

Generalizability across fMRI contrasts

Ideally, researchers would be able to re-use a framework trained to convert statistic maps of a task for another one. Thus, we test the generalizability of the frameworks trained to convert statistic maps from a particular task on statistic maps of other tasks. Here, we explore the generalizability of StarGAN trained on maps of *right-hand* to maps of *right-foot* and *left-hand*.

	fsl-1 → spm-0	spm-0 → fsl-1	fsl-1 → spm-1	fsl-1 → fsl-0
Converting <i>right-foot</i> statistic maps with:				
<i>Initial</i>	86.2	86.3	85.8	95.9
Trained on <i>right-foot</i>	90.5	88.8	88.9	93.1
Trained on <i>right-hand</i>	71.2	71.0	63.0	82.2
Converting <i>left-hand</i> statistic maps with:				
<i>Initial</i>	82.3	82.3	85.9	92.9
Trained on <i>left-hand</i>	88.4	85.4	86.8	85.8
Trained on <i>right-hand</i>	73.2	74.5	69.5	75.2

Table 1: Robustness to distribution shifts (*i.e.* trained and evaluated with statistic maps from different tasks) of StarGAN. Pearson’s correlation (%) computed between generated and ground truth image and averaged across 20 images per transfer. Initial represents the metrics between the source image (before transfer) and the target image.

Table 1 shows the performance of the StarGAN framework trained on *right-hand* statistic maps when applying it to statistic maps of *right-foot* and *left-hand*. We also show the performance of StarGAN trained directly on *right-foot* and *left-hand* for comparison. Our results show that the StarGAN framework does not behave positively when applied to a task different from the task used in the training data: the generated images seem further from the target images (*e.g.* 71.2% for the first transfer between “fsl-1” to “spm-0”) than the source image was from the target (*e.g.* 86.2% in this case). We can see a large performance drop between the framework trained on statistic maps from the task compared to the one trained on maps from another task. Similar observations can be made for generalizability to closer tasks (here, frameworks trained on *right-hand* evaluated on *left-hand*). These results makes us suppose that the mapping from a pipeline to another is different between tasks and thus, if the same model can be used for different subjects on the same task, different models should be trained to transfer statistic maps from tasks unseen during training.